

Misleading arguments about blinding in vitamin C and zinc lozenge trials by Webster et al. (2021)

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Comment on:

Webster RK, Bishop F, Collins GS, Evers AWM, Hoffmann T, Knottnerus JA, Lamb SE, Macdonald H, Madigan C, Napadow V, Price A, Rees JL, Howick J.

Measuring the success of blinding in placebo-controlled trials: Should we be so quick to dismiss it?

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Webster et al. strongly encourage the assessment of whether blinding had been successful in controlled trials. As an example of cautionary examples on the issue, they refer to trials on vitamin C and zinc lozenges for common cold treatment [1].

Webster writes: “*Aside from the importance of blinding itself, the importance of measuring and reporting blinding success is apparent in various trials. For example, **Karlowski, et al [2]** compared vitamin C with placebo for treating the common cold, and found vitamin C to be apparently effective. However, because of the sour taste of vitamin C and sweet taste of the lactose placebo pills, the trial was not successfully blinded. When the authors carried out a subgroup analysis in which they divided participants into those who remained blinded and to those who were not, they found that there was no benefit of vitamin C in the blinded group. Although ideally the authors should have ensured both placebo and active intervention were adequately matched, this example still shows the importance of measuring and reporting blinding success. Otherwise, it would have been mistakenly concluded that vitamin C was superior.*”

However, 25 years ago in the same journal I showed that the Karlowski trial was analyzed erroneously [3,4]. Without any explanations, nearly half of the common cold episodes (105 of 249) were excluded from the subgroup analysis that was done by answers to guessing treatment at the end of the trial. Furthermore, participants were administered therapeutic capsules and regular

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

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capsules. There was no evidence that participants correctly guessed the therapeutic capsules, yet there was, however, stronger evidence of effect for them. Thomas Chalmers, the PI of the Karlowski trial, responded to my reanalysis, but the only error he pointed out was that I had used the term tablets whereas the Karlowski trial had used capsules [5,6].

In our Cochrane review [7], we identified 31 comparisons that examined the effect of regular vitamin C supplementation of at least 0.2 g/day on 9745 episodes of respiratory virus infections occurring during the supplementation period. In adults the duration of colds was reduced by 7.7% (95% CI 3.7% to 11.8%, $P = 0.00018$) and in children by 14.2% (95% CI 7.3% to 21.1%, $P = 0.000053$) [7; Analysis 2.1]. Many trials used citric acid as the placebo and a few trials confirmed that the vitamin C and placebo tablets were indistinguishable. Thus, the findings of the Karlowski trial are consistent with numerous other trials and there is no need to search for non-pharmacological explanations.

Respiratory viruses are a heterogeneous group and their distribution varies over time and location. Therefore, it seems unlikely that the benefit of vitamin C is explained by effects on a certain virus or virus group. Thus, it seemed plausible that vitamin C might also have effects on the new coronavirus [8], and a recent RCT found that vitamin C increased the recovery rate of outpatient cases of SARS-CoV-2 infection by 70% [9]. There are also RCT findings indicating that vitamin C may have effects on more severe diseases [10-12]. It is very unfortunate that this field is ignored because Thomas Chalmers claimed in the middle of the 1970s that vitamin C only has placebo effects [2,4,13-15].

As the second example of the importance of assessing blinding at the end of the trial, Webster wrote: *“More recently, a unsuccessfully blinded trial of zinc for treating common cold symptoms found that zinc significantly reduced the duration of cold symptoms compared to placebo [16]. Whereas, another trial with successful blinding, found that zinc did not reduce symptom duration [17]. This difference may be due to significantly more side-effects being reported to zinc than placebo in the first trial [16], which led to unblinding and subsequent bias.”*

This argument is illogical. First, the Smith trial [17] was published in 1989, whereas the Prasad trial [16] was published in 2000. Thus, it is not possible that the blinding in the earlier Smith trial was improved because of identifying potential flaws in the blinding of the later Prasad trial.

Second, Prasad wrote in the Methods section that *“The placebo and zinc lozenges were identical in weight (4000 mg), appearance, flavor, and texture”* [16]. He also wrote: *“Adequacy of Blinding: Of 20 participants who received zinc, 5% correctly guessed that they were receiving active therapy. Of 20 participants who received placebo, 10% correctly guessed that they were receiving placebo. Therefore, participants did not correctly guess which type of lozenge they were receiving much better than by chance”* [16]. In her critique, Webster does not give any information about what is the basis for arguing that the Prasad (2000) trial was “unsuccessfully blinded” [1].

Third, Smith et al. [17] reported that *“subjects taking zinc gluconate had lower severity scores than those in the corresponding placebo group on days 4 to 7 of treatment. This difference is statistically significant ($P = 0.02$).”* This does not support Webster’s argument that the Smith (1989) trial shows no proof of the benefits of zinc lozenges.

Fourth, Webster et al. ignore potential pharmacological explanations for the difference in the findings. The lozenge used in the Smith (1989) trial [17] contained mannitol and sorbitol [18]. There is experimental evidence indicating that mannitol and sorbitol bind zinc ions in the presence

of saliva, [18] which may explain the rather small effect in the Smith (1989) trial. Furthermore, Dr Smith was one of the authors of the Godfrey (1992) trial [19], which stated in its introduction that “*it has been demonstrated that ... mannitol/sorbitol inactivate zinc by chelation in saliva ... mannitol/sorbitol [zinc lozenge] formulations release no zinc ions when dissolved in the mouth*” and referred to the Smith (1989) trial [17]. This indicates that subsequently Dr Smith did not trust the lozenge formulation of his 1989 trial. Thus, there were improvements in lozenge formulations, but not between the Prasad (2000) lozenges and the Smith (1989) lozenges. Instead, the improvement in formulations was from the Smith (1989) lozenges towards the Godfrey (1992) lozenges, and the latter trial showed significant benefit of zinc lozenges in treating the common cold [19]. The most effective explanations for the heterogeneity in zinc lozenge trial findings are the daily dose of zinc ions and also the excipients used in the lozenge formulations [18,20-23].

It is very unfortunate that the field of zinc lozenges for common cold has been ignored on the basis of speculating that the bad taste of zinc would make patients feel better [1,24,25]. Several meta-analyses of zinc acetate and zinc gluconate lozenges have found an effect on common cold [22,23,26-29].

The most recent RCT on zinc lozenges did not find any apparent benefit, but that finding could be explained by the low dose of zinc, the short duration of the intervention, and the rapid dissolution of the lozenge in the mouth [30]. It is also worth noting that immediately after the stopping of the zinc intervention there was a significant decrease in the rate of recovery in the zinc arm, but an unchanged recovery rate in the placebo arm [30]. This rebound effect is consistent with zinc having effects on colds though it does not support the particular lozenge and dosage.

Carrying out subgroup analysis of variables that have been defined after the start of a trial, and that are potentially linked to pharmacological efficacy, is highly susceptible to bias [3,31,32]. Vitamin C and zinc lozenge trials are very poor examples with which to motivate the encouragement of measuring success of blinding at the later stages of RCTs [1].

References

1. Webster RK, Bishop F, Collins GS, Evers AWM, Hoffmann T, Knottnerus JA, Lamb SE, Macdonald H, Madigan C, Napadow V, Price A, Rees JL, Howick J. Measuring the success of blinding in placebo-controlled trials: Should we be so quick to dismiss it? *J Clin Epidemiol.* 2021;135:176-181.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33662512>
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2021.02.022>
2. Karlowski TR, Chalmers TC, Frenkel LD, Kapikian AZ, Lewis TL, Lynch JM. Ascorbic acid for the common cold. A prophylactic and therapeutic trial. *JAMA.* 1975;231(10):1038-42.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1975.03240220018013>
3. Hemilä H. Vitamin C, the placebo effect, and the common cold: a case study of how preconceptions influence the analysis of results. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 1996;49:1079-84.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356\(96\)00189-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356(96)00189-8)
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225872>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10250/8082>
4. Hemilä H. Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections? [Thesis] University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland, 2006, pp 21-27, 36-38, 45, 63-66.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/20335>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6395595>
5. Chalmers TC. To the preceding article by H. Hemilä. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 1996;49:1085.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356\(96\)00190-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356(96)00190-4)
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225873>

6. Hemilä H. To the dissent by Thomas Chalmers. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 1996;49:1087. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356\(96\)00191-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356(96)00191-6)
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225873>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10250/8079>
7. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C for preventing and treating the common cold. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2013;CD000980.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23440782>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8078152>
<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD000980.pub4>
8. Hemilä H, de Man AME. Vitamin C and COVID-19. *Front Med (Lausanne).* 2021;7:559811.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33537320>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7848027>
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2020.559811>
9. Hemilä H, Carr A, Chalker E. Vitamin C May Increase the Recovery Rate of Outpatient Cases of SARS-CoV-2 Infection by 70%: Reanalysis of the COVID A to Z Randomized Clinical Trial. *Front Immunol.* 2021;12:674681.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34040614>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8141621>
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2021.674681>
10. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C Can Shorten the Length of Stay in the ICU: A Meta-Analysis. *Nutrients.* 2019;11(4):708.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30934660>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6521194>
<https://doi.org/10.3390/nu11040708>
11. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C may reduce the duration of mechanical ventilation in critically ill patients: a meta-regression analysis. *J Intensive Care.* 2020;8:15.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32047636>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7006137>
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40560-020-0432-y>
12. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Reanalysis of the Effect of Vitamin C on Mortality in the CITRIS-ALI Trial: Important Findings Dismissed in the Trial Report. *Front Med (Lausanne).* 2020;7:590853.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33117837>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7575729>
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2020.590853>
13. Hemilä H, Herman ZS. Vitamin C and the common cold: a retrospective analysis of Chalmers' review. *J Am Coll Nutr.* 1995;14(2):116-23.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/07315724.1995.10718483>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/42358>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/15407891>
14. Hemilä H. Vitamin C supplementation and common cold symptoms: problems with inaccurate reviews. *Nutrition.* 1996;12(11-12):804-9.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0899-9007\(96\)00223-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0899-9007(96)00223-7)
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225877>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/14233989>
15. Hemilä H. Thomas Chalmers, vitamin C and the common cold. *J R Soc Med.* 2016;109(2):46.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26880652>
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0141076815606279>
16. Prasad AS, Fitzgerald JT, Bao B, Beck FW, Chandrasekar PH. Duration of symptoms and plasma cytokine levels in patients with the common cold treated with zinc acetate. A randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Ann Intern Med.* 2000;133(4):245-52.
<https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-133-4-200008150-00006>
17. Smith DS, Helzner EC, Nuttall CE Jr, Collins M, Rofman BA, Ginsberg D, Goswick CB, Magner A. Failure of zinc gluconate in treatment of acute upper respiratory tract infections. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 1989;33(5):646-8.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2665639>
<https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.33.5.646>
18. Zarembo JE, Godfrey JC, Godfrey NJ. Zinc(II) in saliva: determination of concentrations produced by different formulations of zinc gluconate lozenges containing common excipients.

- J Pharm Sci. 1992;81(2):128-30.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/jps.2600810205>
19. Godfrey JC, Conant Sloane B, Smith DS, Turco JH, Mercer N, Godfrey NJ. Zinc gluconate and the common cold: a controlled clinical study. *J Int Med Res.* 1992;20(3):234-46.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1397668>
<https://doi.org/10.1177/030006059202000305>
 20. Eby GA. Elimination of efficacy by additives in zinc acetate lozenges for common colds. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2001;32(10):1520.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/320177>
 21. Eby GA. Zinc lozenges: cold cure or candy? Solution chemistry determinations. *Biosci Rep.* 2004;24(1):23-39.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7087920>
 22. Eby GA. Zinc lozenges as cure for the common cold – a review and hypothesis. *Med Hypotheses.* 2010;74(3):482-92.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7173295>
 23. Hemilä H. Zinc lozenges may shorten the duration of colds: a systematic review. *Open Respir Med J.* 2011;5:51-8.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3136969>
 24. Farr BM, Gwaltney JM Jr. The problems of taste in placebo matching: an evaluation of zinc gluconate for the common cold. *J Chronic Dis.* 1987;40(9):875-9.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9681\(87\)90187-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9681(87)90187-1)
 25. Hemilä H. Zinc lozenges and vitamin C for the common cold are not examples of placebo effect in action. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 2015;68(12):1524-5.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2015.05.012>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228079>
 26. Hemilä H, Chalker E. The effectiveness of high dose zinc acetate lozenges on various common cold symptoms: a meta-analysis. *BMC Fam Pract.* 2015;16:24.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25888289>
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12875-015-0237-6>
 27. Hemilä H, Petrus EJ, Fitzgerald JT, Prasad A. Zinc acetate lozenges for treating the common cold: an individual patient data meta-analysis. *Br J Clin Pharmacol.* 2016;82(5):1393-1398.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27378206>
<https://doi.org/10.1111/bcp.13057>
 28. Hemilä H, Fitzgerald JT, Petrus EJ, Prasad A. Zinc Acetate Lozenges May Improve the Recovery Rate of Common Cold Patients: An Individual Patient Data Meta-Analysis. *Open Forum Infect Dis.* 2017;4(2):ofx059.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28480298>
<https://doi.org/10.1093/ofid/ofx059>
 29. Hemilä H. Zinc lozenges and the common cold: a meta-analysis comparing zinc acetate and zinc gluconate, and the role of zinc dosage. *JRSM Open.* 2017;8(5):2054270417694291.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28515951>
<https://doi.org/10.1177/2054270417694291>
See further statistical analysis of the zinc lozenge data:
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35177991>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/41286897>
 30. Hemilä H, Haukka J, Alho M, Vahtera J, Kivimäki M. Zinc acetate lozenges for the treatment of the common cold: a randomised controlled trial. *BMJ Open.* 2020;10(1):e031662.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2019-031662>
 31. Hemilä H. Assessment of blinding may be inappropriate after the trial. *Contemp Clin Trials.* 2005;26:512-4.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cct.2005.04.002>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228099>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10250/7981>
 32. Hemilä H. Analysis of clinical data with breached blindness. *Stat Med.* 2006;25:1434-7.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16572386>
<https://helda.helsinki.fi/handle/10138/228098>